

**THE PECULIARITIES OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT IN RAISING THE
QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE UPDATED
UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. *In Educational Management, the most basic task is to work with the teacher, student, parent and society. The cited descriptions of management indicate that, while it has the meaning of management, administrative commandment is fundamentally different from economic management. Through the development of educational management, it is necessary to change the attitude of people to work, to provide spiritual stimulation and to establish friendly relations between colleagues.*

Keywords: *Management, Management, Leadership, business, fields, knowledge, enterprise, organization, Office, control, maintenance, law, rule, plan, Labor.*

Today, reforms are being carried out in the field of education, among other areas. By default from the education system of the states, the requirement of today is to conduct the proper organization of Education, which is the reason why our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, it is known to us how deeply it makes sense to radically improve the activities of educational institutions, to study the most advanced foreign experience, to create a modern system in all respects, on the basis of today's demand, the idea that no sphere cannot be developed without the development of education, from this point of view, first of all, to, particular attention is paid to educational management, taking into account the fact that it is possible to achieve a result through management and control.

One look at the emergence and stage of development of Educational Management has an ancient history, but the theory of management began to develop only at the beginning of the 20th century. "Management" is translated from the English word *olanga* in the Uzbek language in the sense of organizing, leading management. In the general plan, management denotes management, that is, the organization and management of one or another type of activity (organization and leadership), economic, financial and business sphere in the life of another person.

In the United States, favorable conditions arose at the beginning of the 20th century, when the evolution of scientific management schools began. A huge labor market has appeared in the democratic country. The presence of education helped many intelligent people to show their qualities. New methods of leadership were required. In 1911, Frederick Taylor's book "Principles", which laid the foundation for research in the field of New Science - Leadership.

Proved that group influence can change people's attitude towards Labor. Advised the use of spiritual stimulation in management, for example, the relationship of the employee with colleagues. He urged leaders to focus on community relations, and the school contributed to the separation of Management-in his opinion a separate profession and has two directions.

The first is the study of the problems of enterprise management and the development of modern management concepts.

The second is to study the job duties and functions of managers.

Any leader is called upon to perform certain rainwater functions:

- setting goals for the enterprise and choosing ways to develop;
- classification, distribution of work, creation of organizational structure, selection and placement of personnel, etc;
- employee motivation and coordination, control based on the relationship between managers and the team;
- * normalization, analysis of the work of the enterprise and all workers working in it;
- * motivation depending on the results of work.

Thus, the activities of a modern manager become more complicated. The manager must have knowledge in various fields and apply proven methods in practice. The school solved a number of important management problems that arise everywhere in large-scale industrial production.

The most basic task in management is to work with people. The presented descriptions of management indicate that it is fundamentally different from the economic management of administrative command, while expressing the meaning of management. These differences are as follows:

The first difference is that it concerns the market economy, and administrative command is not a system of carrying out the farm according to the plan.

The second difference arises from the first difference, that is, management in progressive countries is a method of economic management.

The third difference is the difference in management from the management of the socialist system can be determined on the basis of combining the last four descriptions. It can be said that "management is the science and art of effective management." Such management is achieved at the expense of the high qualifications of those engaged in such work, that is, Managers, their erudition, active creative work, initiative, flexibility of thinking, ability to solve tactical and strategic issues, ability to work directly with people. In the Oxford Explanatory Dictionary, the description of management is expressed in the following simple word. It states that "management is a special ability and erudition in the performance of administrative work."

In the present period, it embodies the various requirements for management - management, that is, the method of work, the ability to carry out work, the art of correctly directing the movement of people in joint activities and the requirements for science, without strict administrative requirements, the fulfillment of the specified goal.

In addition to the above qualities, it is appropriate to cite also 2 descriptions in the countries where modern management is in progress:

1-the orientation of the activities of the management corps to obtain a high-quality product corresponding to the consumer's demand (marketing approach in management).

2-The fact that the work of the manager is aimed at increasing the transparency of the organization's team members (humanization of management activities).

Ultimately, the term "management" has one more common meaning, or rather two. It is more commonly used in the sense of crowding, when all organizations designate a team of managers or a Corps of Supreme managers. In such meanings, the word "manager" is usually used when there is a certain opposition between 2 different activities: managers (managers) and manufacturers (workers).

We see that the content of this science is the interaction between the management system and the object of management, the main task of which is to teach students modern methods of management, the secrets of the art of leadership.

Teaching science consists in creating an interest in students in relation to management problems, a passion for practical organizational activities. Because students who are now studying the basics of management will become employees of the future management system, leaders of small and medium, large communities, specialists who are encouraged to develop projects, activities to manage various aspects of the economic, social, organizational and technical activities of enterprises and firms. Management, on the other hand, in most cases depends on the ability of the leader, his ability to work with people, his personal initiative, his understanding. Being able to use all this in management is an art.

The art of management is the ability, mastery, creativity of the manager, leader. Thus, as any creative activity, management has concentrated elements of Science and art in itself.

In conclusion, we can see that the student is one of the guaranteed systems in which young people and students are trained in the future as competitive frames in each area.

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